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BAYOMBONG, NUEVA VIZCAYA, PHILIPPINES

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Title

Status of Students' Post-Pandemic Physical Fitness: Towards a Functional Institution-based Intervention Program

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Abstract

As prescribed by DECS Order No. 58, s. 1990, college students should enroll physical education to complete their degree. More than that, physical education is an integral part of the educational system designed to promote the optimum development of the individual through total body movement in the performance of properly selected physical activities. This study was conducted to determine the post-pandemic performance level of all freshman college students enrolled in FIT HW in AY 2023-2023 in the physical fitness tests designed to measure the fitness level of students in terms of their speed, trunk flexibility, leg power, muscular strength, agility, and endurance and to ascertain the effectiveness of the intervention activities in their post-test. As a descriptive study, data were analyzed using the Standard Physical Fitness Test Transmutation Table, utilizing frequency counts and percentages in describing the respondents' age, sex, BMI, somatotype, physical activity readiness, and overall physical fitness performance level. The results indicate that the respondents were excellent in terms of flexibility. Additionally, an improvement in the respondents' leg strength and power as well as in their agility was observed. The respondent's performance in basic planking revealed that they had excellent general endurance. However, the respondents' performance in the other physical fitness test activities which assess speed, arm strength, abdominal strength, leg strength, and balance ranged from fair to very poor, suggesting the need for improvement. Hence, to ensure the students' growth and development, the conduct of intervention activities should be implemented in an everyday basis. Physical fitness tests and intervention activities should take place not only during the students' PATH FIT classes but should be considered as self-help physical activities that can be carried out even outside their classes. Thus, a module in self-help physical activities is indeed necessary.

Keywords: Physical Fitness Test, Physical Activity Readiness, Gain Scores, Body Mass Index, Somatotype

Introduction

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The Physical Education department of Saint Mary's University serves as a catalyst to promote, encourage, and motivate the development of physical activity, fitness, and sport participation for all Marians. It is the mission of the department to inform the whole populace of the University of the importance of developing and maintaining physical activity and fitness in our daily lives, and to heighten awareness of the links that exist between regular physical activity and good health.

As prescribed by DECS Order No. 58, s. 1990, a college student should undergo Physical Education in general, as a requirement for completion of his degree. As Andin (1988) states, "Physical Education is an integral part of the educational system designed to promote the optimum development of the individual – physically, mentally, socially, and emotionally – through total body movement in the performance of properly selected physical activities" (p. 3).

Saint Mary's University, therefore, parallel to its desire to help or facilitate the development of the potentialities of students offers the four basic PE subjects, namely – Physical Fitness (PE 1), Rhythmic Activities (PE 2), Individual/Dual Sports (PE 3), and Team Sports/Games (PE 4). With the emergence of CMO No. 39 series of 2021 and CMO No. 40 Series of 2021, Physical Education is now termed as Physical Activity Towards Health and Fitness (PATH FIT). Saint Mary's University updated its curriculum in the Academic Year 2018-2019, making the university one of the first schools that offered the PATH FIT subjects even without its CMO, thus, the pioneering school to offer PATH FIT subjects. Presently, the course offering is PATH FIT 1 Health and Wellness (FIT-HW) PATH FIT 2 Combative Sports (FIT CS) PATH FIT 3 Exercise and Dance Program (FIT EP Dance) and PATH FIT 4 Sports (FIT Sp). The curriculum content was noted by CHED R02. A variety of activities are administered in the different PATH FIT subjects. But it is in PATH FIT 1 where students will be able to determine their specific ability in the performance of any related physical education activities through undergoing the Physical Fitness Test.

Individuals may differ in their fitness level. In this regard, all freshmen enrolled in PATH FIT 1 undergo a Physical Fitness Test (PFT) to determine their strengths and weaknesses. The PFT is designed to measure the fitness level of students in terms of their speed, trunk flexibility, leg power, muscular strength, agility, and endurance. Through this test, students will be able to find out their fitness level and be able to fit in their skills to specific activities which will help them become healthy and live a meaningful life.

In the advent of the pandemic, students were forced to experience a sedentary form of life sitting in front of their gadgets for a long period of time, with no physical exertion at all which eventually affected their physical fitness level. Physical fitness is the ability to do one's daily tasks efficiently without undue fatigue but with extra "reserve" energy in case of emergency (Andin, 1988). The physical fitness level of an individual therefore determines the activities that he/she can do. Through this research, the level of physical fitness of the students was assessed by administering a pre-test of the Physical Fitness Test. Intervention activities were conducted based on the pre-test result; after which, a post-test was done to check the improvements in their level of physical fitness, considering the respondents' profile such as gender, age, height, weight, and somatotype, including their physical activity readiness with the aim of creating a fitness program for the students to maintain their physical as well as mental fitness.

RRL and RS and Major Concepts

Theoretical Framework

The present study is grounded on the following theories:

A. Pragmatism

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The principle of pragmatism advocated by John Dewey claims that the meaning of ideas lies in its practical consequences. It means that students must interact with their environment to adapt and learn. This philosophy is very much related to experimentalism. It is derived from the Greek '*pragma*' meaning a thing done, a fact that is practiced. According to the pragmatist, the aim of education is the total development of the child through experiencing or through self-activity or the *learning by doing*. Pragmatists also suggest that the curriculum must offer subjects or provide opportunities for various projects and activities that are relevant to the needs, abilities, and interests as well as the socio-economic conditions of the learners. They further believe that it must be learner-centered for all educative process. This concept is based on Dewey's principle stating that education is life, education is growth, education is a social process and education is the construction of human experience (Duka, 1999).

According to Tamayo (2013), learning to do is the development of the hand and focus on skills and actions. This requires person to act properly in any kind of situation. Learning to do implies that students learn best when they do or apply what they know. This is related to the principle of Confucius: *I hear and I forget. I see and I remember. I do and I understand*. Learning to do is very much related to learning by doing as supported by John Dewey.

B. Observational Learning

Performers learn new competencies by observing others. They learn through demonstrations that can be used as role models to follow (Bandura, 1977). According to him, there are four stages of this theory such as the following: attention in which the performers need to watch suitable demonstration of the skill; retention which refers to creating the mental image of the necessary skill. In this stage, practicing the mind skill over and over can help make the right movements in the right order. The third stage is motor production in which students must be able to repeat the skills first or through a series of progressions; and lastly the motivation needed by the learners for them to replicate the skilled action.

Andin (1988) argues that through carefully selected physical education activities, an individual who participates actively will develop and maintain good health and a high level of physical fitness. The acquisition of physical skills can motivate an individual to participate further in physical activities, hence, his growth and development will be enhanced. Physical fitness, being the primary specific objective in teaching physical education, should be stressed.

Weight for height, Height Matters, Weight for Age

Anonas (1997) conducted a study across regions. The survey showed that the highest number (95.8%) with normal weight for their height among children 0-5 years old are in Eastern Visayas and CARAGA. Central Visayas (95.7%) and the Davao Peninsula (95.3%) followed closely. Meanwhile, NCR has the greatest number of overweight children (6.4%) in relation to their height, followed by ARMM (2.9%), and the Northern Mindanao (2.0%). Researchers did not find any significant number of overweight children in Western Mindanao and CAR. Overall, 93 percent of Filipino children have normal weight for height ratio, and only 2 percent are overweight.

In terms of height for age, 72.5 percent is normal, 26.3 percent is stunted, and 1.2 percent is considered tall for their age. Soccksargen had the greatest number of children with stunted growth at 40.5 percent followed by Western Mindanao (37.4%), and ARMM (36.1%). Central Luzon has the greatest number

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of children with normal height for their age at 79 percent, trailed by Ilocos (78.6%), and Calabarzon (77.2%). Children who are too tall for their age mostly come from NCR (2.4%), ARMM (2.1%), and Calabarzon (1.8%).

In terms of weight compared to age, 73.5 percent of Filipino children are normal, 24.6 percent are too light for their age, while 2 percent are too heavy for their age. Most children with normal weight for their age come from CAR (82.5%), Cagayan Valley (81.4%), and NCR (78.6%). Meanwhile, children who are underweight for their age come from ARMM (38%), Mindoro-Marinduque-Romblon-Palawan (35.8%), and Western Mindanao (33.9%).

Somatotype theory

A bodybuilder would fit the definition of mesomorphic. Using anthropometric methods, Sheldon (2011) studied the photographed bodies of some 4,000 men from front view, side view, and back view. He concluded that the physique of men can be divided into the contribution of three fundamental elements: the somatotypes. He named the somatotypes after the three germ layers of embryonic development: the endoderm, that develops into the digestive tract, the mesoderm, the layer that becomes muscle, heart and blood vessels, and the ectoderm that forms the nervous system. Sheldon's (1940) "somatotypes" and their (presumed and supposed) associated psychological traits can be summarized as follows:

Ectomorphic body type is characterized by long arms and legs and a short upper body, high forehead, slightly narrow shoulders, and supposedly have a higher proportion of nervous tissue. They also have long and thin muscles. Ectomorphs usually have a very low-fat storage; therefore, they are usually referred to as slim. Ectomorphs are also subject to more changeable moods due to the lack of body sugars to regulate the hormones; they are also considered weaker and less desirable compared to meso or endomorphs who are genetically more likely to provide healthier offspring. Mesomorphic body type is characterized by a high rate of muscle growth and a higher proportion of muscular tissue. They have large bones, solid torso combined with low fat levels. It is also noted that they have wide shoulders with a narrow waist. Endomorphic body type is characterized by an increased amount of fat storage, due to having a larger number of fat cells than the average person, as well as higher proportion of digestive tissue. They have a wide waist and a large bone structure. In his book, *Atlas of Men*, Sheldon (1940) categorized all possible body types according to a scale ranging from 1 to 7 for each of the somatotypes, where the pure endomorph is 7-1-1, the pure mesomorph 1-7-1 and the pure ectomorph scores 1-1-7. From type number, an individual's mental characteristics could supposedly be predicted. Sheldon's (1940) research showed that a predisposition towards criminality might be influenced by a somatotype high in endomorphy and intermediate in mesomorphy, and in contrast, a predisposition towards suicidality might be influenced by a somatotype high in ectomorphy; on the other hand, ectomorphs were found to be more common in mental institutions.

These sources have relation to the present study because they show the importance of the roles of the teachers and administrators in improving the quality of the physical education program.

In the study of Aquino (1999), his findings revealed that for the 15-year-old respondents, the variables sex, height, and weight significantly correlated with the following physical fitness performance of pupils: standing long jump, curl-up, 50-m run, pull-up, sit and reach, and 1000-meter run. However, sex is not a significant factor that influence physical fitness in shuttle run.

Villaranda (2001), in her study, found that the underweight, overweight, and under height intermediate pupils in the division of Legazpi City had a lower performance level than those pupils with

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average height and weight. This also affected their rating in physical education as they had lower performance level with regard to psychomotor activities.

Salangsang (1994) noted in her study that 16-year-old students performed significantly better than the 12-year-old students, but were lesser performers than the 13-, 14-, and 15-year-old students. Muscles of grownup boys and girls were more developed, making them more ready for more strenuous activities.

Casals et al. (2015) found in their study that in the Mann-Whitney comparisons by sex and age category males had significantly have higher muscle mass and lower fat mass than females. Linear regression models indicated that sex, age category, and body mass significantly predicted Special Judo Fitness Test Level index. Model 3 which included body compositions and somatotypes were predictors. Higher muscle and bone masses and lower ectomorphy were associated with better Special Judo Fitness Test Level performance.

In addition, the study of Minatto et al. (2016) indicated the importance of cardiorespiratory fitness in adolescents. However, it is necessary to systematize how intervention strategies and methodological characteristics of studies influence the effects of CRF interventions. Results revealed that the effect size varied according to the age group, sample size, intervention environment, strategies in experimental groups, CRF priority in the study, CRF indicator, session length, weekly frequency, intervention duration and presentation of results. The study concluded that interventions in the school environment seem to have positive effect on CRF among adolescents, but there is high heterogeneity between studies. Some intervention activities can be used to better improve the CRF of the students such as exercise sessions in addition to physical education classes, combination of aerobic and resistance exercises, frequency of three times weekly and intensity control.

These studies made the researchers interested in finding out if the same studies may also be done in Saint Mary's University, with the college freshmen as the respondents. The researchers surveyed the profile of the respondents as to gender, age, height, weight, somatotype with performance in the physical fitness test. Scores were determined and transmuted using the Standardized Physical Fitness Test Transmutation Table.

Conceptual Framework

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Figure 1. Conceptual framework of the study

Figure 1 shows the conceptual framework of the study illustrating how the Fitness Program was developed. Profile (PARQ+), pre-test, intervention activities, and post-test are the key variables in developing the fitness program. The researchers utilized a survey questionnaire in all FIT HW Classes of 1st semester of the School Year 2022-2023. The pre-test was administered as an initial assessment of the fitness status of the respondents. In line with the result of the pre-test, intervention activities were conducted. These activities can enhance their PFT performance that ensures rehabilitation of their weaknesses and improvement of their strength. The post-test commenced before the semester ends. And the result of which were compared to the result of their pre-test. Therefore, the results of this study became the basis of developing the fitness program.

The physical fitness test is a battery of inexpensive and easy-to-administer activities. These activities were chosen based on the criteria that they should measure the components of physical fitness and should be administered with a minimal use of equipment. It should also offer appropriate actual activities for fitness development and maintenance.

The different activities or items in the physical fitness test are (1) 40-meter sprint, (2) sit and reach, (3) standing long jump, (4) curl-ups, (5) push-up, (6) basic planking, (7) zipper test, (8) stork balance test, (9) shuttle run. This study was conceptualized based on the premise that the profile of the students has a significant influence on their physical fitness performance level.

Statement of the Problem / Purpose of the Study

This study aimed to determine the profile and post-pandemic physical fitness performance level of FIT HW students at Saint Mary's University during the first semester of the school year 2022-2023.

Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of FIT HW students in terms of:
 - 1.1 age

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- 1.2 sex
- 1.3 body mass index rages
- 1.4 somatotype
2. What is the physical activity readiness of the respondents based on the PARQ+ form?
3. What is the physical fitness performance level of FIT HW students in terms of:
 - 2.1 40-meter sprint
 - 2.2 sit and reach
 - 2.3 standing long jump
 - 2.4 curl-up
 - 2.5 push-up
 - 2.6 basic Planking
 - 2.7 zipper test
 - 2.8 Stork Balance Test
 - 2.9 Shuttle Run

Methodology

A. Design

This study employed the descriptive survey method since it is a description of the FIT HW students in terms of their personal profile, such as age, sex, Body Mass Index, somatotype, physical activity readiness and their physical fitness performance level.

B. Locale

This study was conducted during the first semester of the school year 2022-2023 at Saint Mary's University (SMU), Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya.

C. Participants and Sample

The subjects of this study were the 1, 148 FIT HW students enrolled in FIT HW subject from the four schools namely School of Teacher Education and Humanities (STEH), School of Engineering and Architecture and Information Technology (SEAIT), School of Health and Natural Sciences. (SHaNS), and School of Accountancy and Business, (SAB). Total sample technique was utilized in this study.

D. Instrument(s)

The main instruments used in this study were the Physical Activity Readiness Questionnaire (PARQ+) Form 2022 and Physical Fitness Card of the respondents. The survey form contains the different activities in each physical fitness component to be executed by the students. It is divided into two categories (*Health Related and Skill Related components*) where some of the activities made use of a timer/stopwatch and ruler/meter sticks for the other activities. Moreover, pre-test and post-test were administered using the same form/score card.

E. Data Gathering Procedure

The personal profile of the respondents such as age, sex, body mass index (BMI), somatotype, and their physical fitness performance level was obtained from their Physical Fitness Test Cards that they used

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in their FIT HW classes. The Physical Activity Readiness Questionnaire (PAR-Q+) was the source of information of student's readiness to undergo physical activities.

To measure the physical fitness level of the students, a standardized Physical Fitness Test which contained 10 activities such as 40-m sprint (speed), sit and reach (trunk flexibility), standing long jump (leg power), sit-up/curl-up (abdominal strength and muscular endurance), basic flanking, zipper test, stork balance test, shuttle run, step test (cardio-respiratory endurance) and push-up (upper body strength) was administered in the pre-test and post-test. The pre-test was conducted during the 1st term and the post-test was conducted during the 1st week of the 3rd term. Scores were determined and transmuted using the Standardized Physical Fitness Test Transmutation Table. In the pre-test, if the students deviated in a specific activity, intervention was done by administering related activities that would help the students develop and enhance their skill, thus getting a better score in the post-test. The result of the physical fitness test was the basis of Fitness Program and the administration of activities in their next PATH FIT Subjects.

F. Treatment of Data

The researchers utilized the following statistical tools in the treatment of the data gathered in this study:

For descriptive analysis, frequency counts, percentage and ranks were used describing the data in terms of the personal profile of the respondents such as: age, sex, BMI, somatotype, and their physical fitness performance level and physical activity readiness.

For the result of the pre-test and post-test, the Standardized Physical Fitness Test Transmutation was used.

The following tables show the Scale on Fitness Test Standards:

**Scale on Fitness Test Standards
(15-29 years old)**

Table 1
Scale on Fitness test Standard for Male

PF Test	Superior	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor	Very Poor
1. Sit and Reach	Above 23	22-23	20-21	17-19	14-16	12-13	Below 12
2. Standing Long Jump	Above 300	251-300	201-250	176-200	151-175	91-150	Below 91
3. 60-sec. sit-up	Above 55	51-55	48-50	42-47	36-41	17-35	0-16
4. Push-up/Modified	Above 54	51-54	45-50	35-44	25-34	20-24	0-19

Table 2
Scale on Fitness Test Standard for Female

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PF Test	Superior	Excellent	Very Good	Good	Average	Poor	Very Poor
Sit and Reach	Above 23	22-23	20-21	17-19	14-16	12-13	Below 12
Standing Long Jump	Above 220	201-220	171-200	151-170	131-150	51-130	Below 51
60-sec. sit-up	Above 47	43-47	36-42	33-35	29-32	14-28	0-13
Push-up/Modified	Above 48	46-48	34-45	17-33	10-16	6-9	0-5

Table 3
Scale on Zipper Test for Male and Female

Score	Standard	Interpretation
5	Fingers overlapped by 6 cm. and above	Excellent
4	Fingers overlapped by 4-5.9 cm.	Very Good
3	Fingers overlapped by 2-3.9 cm.	Good
2	Fingers overlapped by 0.1-1.9 cm.	Fair
1	Just touched the fingers	Needs Improvement
0	Gap of 0.1 or wider	Poor

Table 4
Scale on Stork Balance Test for Male and Female

Score	Age					Interpretation
	9-12	13-14	15-16	17 and above		
5	41 - 60 sec.	81 - 100 sec.	121 - 150 sec.	161 - 180 sec.	Excellent	
4	31 - 40 sec.	61 - 80 sec.	91 - 120 sec.	121 - 160 sec.	Very Good	
3	21 - 30 sec.	41 - 60 sec.	61 - 90 sec.	81 - 120 sec.	Good	
2	11 - 2 sec.	21 - 40 sec.	31 - 60 sec.	41 - 80 sec.	Fair	
1	1 - 10 sec.	1 - 20 sec.	1 - 30 sec.	1 - 40 sec.	Needs Improvement	

Table 5
Scale for 40 - Meter Sprint

Age	Standard Norms in Seconds							
	Boys				Girls			
	9 - 12	13 - 14	15 - 16	17 & above	9 - 12	13 - 14	15 - 16	17 & above
Excellent	<6.0	<5.0	<4.5	<4.0	<7.0	<6.5	<5.5	<4.5
Very good	6.1 - 7.7	5.1 - 6.9	4.6 - 5.4	4.1 - 5.4	7.1 - 8.4	6.6 - 7.6	5.6 - 6.1	4.6 - 5.9
Good	7.8 - 8.5	7.0 - 8.0	5.5 - 7.0	5.5 - 6.5	8.5 - 9.5	7.7 - 8.8	6.2 - 7.2	6.0 - 7.0
Fair	9.5 - 8.6	8.1 - 9.1	7.1 - 8.1	6.6 - 7.5	9.6 - 10.5	8.9 - 9.5	7.3 - 8.5	7.1 - 8.1
Needs Improvement	>9.6	>9.2	>8.2	>7.6	>10.6	>9.6	>8.6	>8.2

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Table 6
Scale for Basic Plank for Male and Female

Score	Standard	Interpretation
5	51 seconds and above	Excellent
4	46 – 50 seconds	Very Good
3	31 – 45 seconds	Good
2	16 – 30 seconds	Fair
1	1 – 15 seconds	Needs Improvement

Table 7
Scale for Shuttle Run for Male and Female

Standard	Interpretation	Score
10-15	Excellent	5
16-20	Very Good	4
21-25	Good	3
26-30	Needs Improvement	2
31-above	Poor	1

G. Ethical Considerations

The proposal was submitted to Saint Mary’s University Research Ethics Board (SMUREB) at Saint Mary’s University, Ponce Street, DMM, Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya with cellphone number: 09177053041 and email: reb@smu.edu.ph. for approval.

During the first week of classes, the respondents were informed that one of the activities that they would be subjected to a Physical Fitness Test, which was also a subject requirement. Before that, they were given a PAR-Q+ Form to determine their fitness to participate in the activities. Because there will be a pre- and post-test, they were also informed that the results will be the primary focus of the study. The researchers were PATH-FIT Instructors, and they have promised to keep the information/results obtained from the forms strictly confidential.

Respondents in this study were first-year college students enrolled in FIT HW during the first semester of A.Y 2022-2023. In identifying the participants, the researchers:

- a. let their students answer the PAR-Q+ form and let their parents/guardians signed it;
- b. identified who was fit to perform the activities based on the PAR-Q+ form;
- c. informed them that they will be the subject of the study;
- d. distributed ICF to ensure their autonomy in deciding to participate in the study.

There are numerous Physical Fitness Test activities that participants could participate in; however, the researchers considered their capability and safety. As a result, they identified nine activities that anyone could do. Participants identified their strengths and weaknesses in the components of Physical Fitness through these activities. And with that, they already have a better idea on how to address these concerns.

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The PFT was divided into two categories, indoor and outdoor. The indoor category took place in the gymnasium, while the latter took place at the University oval. The teacher administered it by grouping students and providing them with materials. PFT forms were distributed for the students to record the outcomes of their activities. Moreover, to secure the results of their activities, PFT forms were collected by the teacher after the meeting.

Results and Discussions

Profile of FIT HW Students in Terms of Age, Sex, Pre-test BMI Ranges, Post-Test BMI Ranges, Pre-test Somatotype, and Post-test Somatotype, :

Table 8
Profile of FIT HW Students in Terms of Age

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
17.00	169	14.7	14.7	14.7
18.00	544	47.4	47.4	62.1
19.00	166	14.5	14.5	76.6
20.00	135	11.8	11.8	88.3
21.00	129	11.2	11.2	99.6
22.00	5	.4	.4	100.0
Total	1148	100.0	100.0	

Table 8 shows that the age of the respondents ranged from 17 to 22 years old. Further, as indicated in the table, most respondents in the study were 18 years old and only a few were 22 years old.

Table 9
Profile of FIT HW Students in Terms of Sex

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Male	386	33.6	33.6	33.6
Female	762	66.4	66.4	100.0

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Total	1148	100.0	100.0
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Based on Table 9, from a total of 1148 respondents, female respondents dominated the population more than the male. The number of females was almost twice the number of male among the respondents.

Table 10
Profile of FIT HW Students in Terms of Body Mass Index in the Pre-test

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
UNDERWEIGHT	586	51.0	51.0	51.0
NORMAL	436	38.0	38.0	89.0
OVERWEIGHT	97	8.4	8.4	97.5
OBESE	29	2.5	2.5	100.0
Total	1148	100.0	100.0	

Table 9 displays the four categories in which the respondents were classified according to their body mass index during the pre-test. As seen in the table, it is alarming to note that a little more than half of the total population was categorized as underweight (51%; BMI=18.5 or below). Those who were classified as normal were less than half of the population (38%; BMI=18.6-25.5). It can be noted that less than 10% of the students were overweight (8.4%; BMI 25.6 – 29.5) and only a few were considered obese (2.5%; BMI= 30 or higher). The presence of underweight and obese students may be attributed to their unhealthy lifestyle.

Table 11
Profile of FIT HW Students in Terms of Body Mass Index in the Post-test

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
UNDERWEIGHT	602	52.4	52.4	52.4
NORMAL	436	38.0	38.0	90.4
OVERWEIGHT	86	7.5	7.5	97.9
OBESE	24	2.1	2.1	100.0
Total	1148	100.0	100.0	

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In Table 11, the results of the BMI of the students in the post-test are presented. It can be gleaned from the table that there was an increase in the number of underweight students by 16 as compared with the pre-test in Table 10. However, students who were categorized as normal remained the same. It can be noted that the number of students who were overweight decreased by 11 and those who were obese decreased by 5.

Table 12
Profile of FIT HW Students in Terms of Somatotype in the Pre-test

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
ECTOMORPH	728	63.4	63.4	63.4
MESOMORPH	297	25.9	25.9	89.3
ENDOMORPH	123	10.7	10.7	100.0
Total	1148	100.0	100.0	

Table 12 displays the three body types based on the respondents' BMI. The largest portion of the overall population (728) was categorized as ectomorphic implying that almost 65% of the students had slender and tiny body build with a higher surface area to mass ratio. Almost 300 students were considered mesomorphic body type characterized by a predominance of muscles with big and hefty bones. Finally, the table shows that almost 11% of the respondents were classified as endomorphic body type characterized by a predominance of soft roundness and large digestive viscera.

Table 13
Profile of FIT HW Students in Terms of Somatotype in the Post-test

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
ECTOMORPH	719	62.6	62.6	62.6
MESOMORPH	313	27.3	27.3	89.9
ENDOMORPH	116	10.1	10.1	100.0
Total	1148	100.0	100.0	

In Table 13, the respondents' body types are shown after they performed the PFT post-test. As seen in the table, most of the students were classified as ectomorphs, but lower in number as compared to the result in the pre-test. An increase of 16 students can be noticed in the number of mesomorphs as compared

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to the result in the pre-test. However, in terms of those who were classified as endomorph, a decrease of 7 can be observed comparing the pre-test and post-test. Furthermore, the results in the table are consistent with the results in Table 12, with the ectomorph having the highest proportion and endomorph having the lowest.

2. The Physical Activity Readiness of the Respondents Based on the PARQ+ Form

The succeeding discussion dwells on the results of the physical readiness of the respondents as reflected in the PARQ+ Form that they answered. The form contains seven questions to determine the respondents' readiness for the physical activities.

Table 14
Results of the Respondents' Physical Activity Readiness

Question number	Question	YES		NO	
		f	%	f	%
1	Has your doctor ever said that you have a heart condition OR high blood pressure?	19	1.7	1129	98.3
2	Do you feel pain in your chest at rest, during your daily activities of living, OR when you do physical activity?	128	11.1	1020	88.9
3	Do you lose balance because of dizziness OR have you lost consciousness in the last 12 months? Please answer NO if your dizziness was associated with over-breathing (including during vigorous exercise).	79	6.9	1069	93.1
4	Have you ever been diagnosed with another chronic medical condition (other than heart disease or high blood pressure)? PLEASE LIST CONDITION(S) HERE:	35	3.0	1113	97.0
5	Are you currently taking prescribed medications for a chronic medical condition? PLEASE LIST CONDITION(S) AND MEDICATIONS HERE:	21	1.8	1127	98.2
6	Do you currently have (or have had within the past 12 months) a bone, joint, or soft tissue? (Muscle, ligament, or tendon) problem that could be made worse by becoming more physically active? Please answer NO if you had a problem in the past, but it does not limit your current ability to be physically active. PLEASE LIST CONDITION(S) HERE:	14	1.2	1134	98.8
7	Has your doctor ever said that you should only do medically supervised physical activity?	7	.6	1141	99.4

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Table 14 displays the responses of the students to the Physical Activity Readiness Questionnaire before doing the indicated physical fitness test activities. There are seven general health questions answered by the students. The results derived from this questionnaire determine who can and cannot do the physical fitness test. In question 1, almost 2% (1.7%) of the 1148 respondents said they had a cardiac disease or excessive blood pressure. Moreover, more than 10% (11.1%) respondents claimed that they had pain in their chest during rest and throughout everyday activities. In terms of question 3, almost 7% (6.9%) respondents said they had lost their balance due to dizziness or had lost consciousness in the previous 12 months. Respondents were also asked if they had ever been diagnosed with another chronic medical illness, and only a few (3.0%) responded in the affirmative. In addition, only a few (1.8%) students said yes to the question, *Are you now taking prescription meds for a chronic medical condition?* Question 5 is related to bone/structural state. To this question, a little higher than 1% (1.2%) of answered yes. The final question has something to do with the doctor's advice that they should only engage in medically supervised physical activity. To this question only seven (.6%) of those polled responded positively. Based on the data, the respondents were generally ready to undertake the physical activities prepared for the study.

The respondents who answered yes to the seven questions in Table 14 were asked to the answer questions indicated in Table 15 to follow up the respondents' medical conditions.

Table 15
Results of the Follow-up Questions about the Respondents' Medical Conditions

Question number	Question	YES		NO	
		f	%	f	%
1	Do you have Arthritis, Osteoporosis, or Back Problems?	23	2.0	1119	97.5
1a	Do you have difficulty controlling your condition with medications or other physician-prescribed therapies? (Answer NO if you are not currently taking medications or other treatments)	5	.4	1141	99.4
1b	Do you have joint problems causing pain, a recent fracture or fracture caused by osteoporosis or cancer, displaced vertebra (e.g., spondylolisthesis), and/or spondylolysis/pars defect (a crack in the bony ring on the back of the spinal column)?	8	.7	1140	99.3
1c	Have you had steroid injections or taken steroid tablets regularly for more than 3 months?	30	2.6	1118	97.4
2	Do you currently have Cancer of any kind? If the above condition(s) is/are present, answer questions 2a-2b	0	0	1148	100.0
2a	Does your cancer diagnosis include any of the following types: lung/bronchogenic, multiple myeloma (cancer of plasma cells), head, and/or neck?	0	0	1148	100.0
2b	Are you currently receiving cancer therapy (such as chemotherapy or radiotherapy)?	0	0	1148	100.0

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3	Do you have a Heart or Cardiovascular Condition? This includes Coronary Artery Disease, Heart Failure, Diagnosed Abnormality of Heart Rhythm If the above condition(s) is/are present, answer questions 3a-3d	7	.6	1141	99.4
3a	Do you have difficulty controlling your condition with medications or other physician-prescribed therapies? (Answer NO if you are not currently taking medications or other treatments)	2	.2	1146	99.8
3b	Do you have an irregular heartbeat that requires medical management? (e.g., atrial -brillation, premature ventricular contraction)	7	.6	1141	99.4
3c	Do you have chronic heart failure?	1	.1	1147	99.9
3d	Do you have diagnosed coronary artery (cardiovascular) disease and have not participated in regular physical activity in the last 2 months?	2	.2	1146	99.8
4	Do you currently have High Blood Pressure? If the above condition(s) is/are present, answer questions 4a-4b	2	.2	1146	99.8
4a	Do you have difficulty controlling your condition with medications or other physician-prescribed therapies? (Answer NO if you are not currently taking medications or other treatments)	1	.1	1147	99.9
4b	Do you have a resting blood pressure equal to or greater than 160/90 mmHg with or without medication? (Answer YES if you do not know your resting blood pressure)	1	.1	1147	99.9
5	Do you have any Metabolic Conditions? This includes Type 1 Diabetes, Type 2 Diabetes, Pre-Diabetes If the above condition(s) is/are present, answer questions 5a-5e	2	.2	1144	99.7
5a	You often have difficulty controlling your blood sugar levels with foods, medications, or other physician-prescribed therapies?	2	.2	1146	99.8
5b	Do you often suffer from signs and symptoms of low blood sugar (hypoglycemia) following exercise and/or during activities of daily living? Signs of hypoglycemia may include shakiness, nervousness, unusual irritability, abnormal sweating, dizziness or light-headedness, mental confusion, difficulty speaking, weakness, or sleepiness	9	.8	1139	99.2
5c	Do you have any signs or symptoms of diabetes complications such as heart or vascular disease and/or complications affecting your eyes, kidneys, OR the sensation in your toes and feet?	0	0	1148	100.0

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5d	Do you have other metabolic conditions (such as current pregnancy-related diabetes, chronic kidney disease, or liver problems)?	0	0	1148	100.0
5e	Are you planning to engage in what for you is unusually high (or vigorous) intensity exercise in the near future	6	.5	1142	99.5
6	Do you have any Mental Health Problems or Learning Difficulties? This includes Alzheimer's, Dementia, Depression, Anxiety Disorder, Eating Disorder, Psychotic Disorder, Intellectual Disability, Down Syndrome If the above condition(s) is/are present, answer questions 6a-6b	5	.4	1143	99.6
6a	Do you have difficulty controlling your condition with medications or other physician-prescribed therapies? (Answer NO if you are not currently taking medications or other treatments)	4	.3	1144	99.7
6b	Do you have Down Syndrome AND back problems affecting nerves or muscles?	0	0	1148	100.0
7	Do you have a respiratory disease? This includes Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease, Asthma, Pulmonary High Blood Pressure If the above condition(s) is/are present, answer questions 7a-7d	5	.4	1143	99.6
7a	Do you have difficulty controlling your condition with medications or other physician-prescribed therapies? (Answer NO if you are not currently taking medications or other treatments)	3	.3	1145	99.7
7b	Has your doctor ever said your blood oxygen level is low at rest or during exercise and/or that you require supplemental oxygen therapy?	4	.3	1144	99.7
7c	If asthmatic, do you currently have symptoms of chest tightness, wheezing, labored breathing, consistent cough (more than 2 days/week), or have you used your rescue medication more than twice in the last week?	40	3.5	1108	96.5
7d	Has your doctor ever said you have high blood pressure in the blood vessels of your lungs?	0	0	1148	100.0
8	Do you have a Spinal Cord Injury? This includes Tetraplegia and Paraplegia If the above condition(s) is/are present, answer questions 8a-8c	5	.4	1143	99.6
8a	Do you have difficulty controlling your condition with medications or other physician-prescribed therapies? (Answer NO if you are not currently taking medications or other treatments)	1	.1	1147	99.9

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8b	Do you commonly exhibit low resting blood pressure significant enough to cause dizziness, light-headedness, and/or fainting?	6	.5	1142	99.5
8c	Has your physician indicated that you exhibit sudden bouts of high blood pressure (known as Autonomic Dyslexia)?	0	0	1148	100.0
9	Have you had a Stroke? This includes Transient Ischemic Attack (TIA) or Cerebrovascular Even If the above condition(s) is/are present, answer questions 9a-9	0	0	1148	100.0
9a	Do you have difficulty controlling your condition with medications or other physician-prescribed therapies? (Answer NO if you are not currently taking medications or other treatments)	0	0	1148	100.0
9b	Do you have any impairment in walking or mobility?	0	0	1148	100.0
9c	Y9C. Have you experienced a stroke or impairment in nerves or muscles in the past 6 months?	0	0	1148	100.0
10	Do you have any other medical condition not listed above or do you have two or more medical conditions? If you have other medical conditions, answer questions 10a-10c	2	.2	1146	99.8
10a	Have you experienced a blackout, fainted, or lost consciousness as a result of a head injury within the last 12 months OR have you had a diagnosed concussion within the last 12 months?	6	.5	1142	99.5
10b	Do you have a medical condition that is not listed (such as epilepsy, neurological conditions, kidney problems)?	9	.8	1139	99.2
10c	Do you currently live with two or more medical conditions?	7	.6	1141	99.4

Table 15 presents the respondents' responses to the follow-up questions about their medical conditions. As mentioned in the preceding paragraph, only those who answered yes to the seven questions in Table 14 continued to answer these follow-up questions. As can be seen in the table, 12 questions were answered affirmatively by the respondents. It is interesting to note that 40 respondents have asthmatic condition and that they are currently have symptoms of chest tightness, wheezing, labored breathing, consistent cough and have used rescue medication for more than twice in the last week. This result is very relevant in decision-making as regards the students' participation in the physical activities. Additionally, nine of them admitted that they have other medical conditions such as epilepsy, neurological conditions, and kidney problems. Six of the respondents divulged that they have currently two or more medical conditions. Further, six respondents admitted that they have experienced a blackout or loss of consciousness as a result

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of head injury within the last 12 months and have been diagnosed with concussion within the last 12 months. Similarly, this result is critical in allowing these students or not to participate in the physical activities. Further, only six respondents admitted having low blood pressure that causes dizziness, light-headedness, and/or fainting. Surprisingly, only six respondents were eager to engage in more abnormally high intensity exercise in the near future. Overall, the majority of the respondents are still capable of performing the physical fitness test exercises.

3. The Performance Level of FIT HW Students in the Physical Fitness Tests

The following tables and discussions present the results of the respondents' level of performance in the physical fitness tests that they performed during the pre-test and the post-test.

One of the physical fitness activities that the respondents performed in the tests was the 40-meter sprint. In this activity, the speed of the students was tested as they ran to the finish line as fast as they could. The performance of each respondent was recorded in seconds.

Table 16
Male Respondents' Performance Level in the 40-Meter Sprint in Pre-test and Post-test

Level of Performance	f	Pre-Test		Post-Test		
		Percent	Valid %	f	Percent	Valid %
NEEDS IMPROVEMENT	101	26.2	26.2	131	33.9	33.9
FAIR	114	29.5	29.5	90	23.3	23.3
GOOD	133	34.5	34.5	148	38.3	38.3
VERY GOOD	12	3.1	3.1	0	0	0
EXCELLENT	26	6.7	6.7	17	4.4	4.4
Total	386	100.0	100.0	386	100.0	100.0

Table 16 reveals the level of performance of male respondents in the sprint activity during their pre-test and post-test. Comparing the results, it can be observed that there was an increase in the number of male respondents who needed improvement in the sprint activity in the post-test. Almost 30% of the students need improvement because they were able to the sprint in more than 7.6 seconds. Similar observation can be seen among those whose level of performance was good. Almost 35 % of the total population was rated good because they were able to perform such physical activity within 5.5 – 6.5 seconds. It is interesting to note that no one was considered very good in the post-test while there were at least 12 respondents who were rated very good in the pre-test. This means that these students were the only ones who were able to the 40-meter sprint in the pre-test within 4.1-5.4 seconds. On the other hand, a decrease in the number of respondents can be seen in those with fair and excellent performances in the post-test as compared to the pre-test. This implies that only a few students did remarkably well in the pre-test but, but somehow did not

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fare well in the post test. However, the overall picture implies that most respondents were rated good in sprint both in the pre-test and post-test among the male.

Table 17
Female Respondents' Performance Level in the 40-Meter Sprint in Pre-test and Post-test

Level of performance	%	Percent	Valid Percent	%	Percent	Valid Percent
NEEDS IMPROVEMENT	387	50.7	50.7	340	44.6	44.6
FAIR	211	27.7	27.7	223	29.2	29.2
GOOD	98	12.8	12.8	144	18.9	18.9
VERY GOOD	43	5.6	5.6	23	3.0	3.0
EXCELLENT	24	3.1	3.1	33	4.3	4.3
Total	763	100.0	100.0	763	100.0	100.0

Table 17 displays the results of the pre-test and post-test in sprint among the female respondents. It can be noted that the highest level of performance in sprint was only earned by less than 5% of the female respondents in both tests. This implies that only a few were able to perform the activity in less than 4.5 seconds. It is apparent that the number of students whose performance was excellent increased during the post-test. Similar to the male respondents, most female respondents (pre-test=50.7%; post-test=44.6%) needed improvement in sprint because they did the activity in more than 8.2 seconds although the number decreased during the post-test. An increase in the number of students can also be observed among those who were rated good in both tests (pre-test=12.8; post-test=18.9). A percentage of 3.1 was added to those who were able to do the sprint within 6.0-7.0 seconds. The overall result implies that the female respondents' level of performance in sprint in both tests ranged from needs improvement to fair. Hence, there is a need for the students to practice and perform sprint as one of the physical fitness activities to make them fit and well.

The second physical fitness activity done by the respondents was sit and reach, which measures linear flexibility and helps measure the extensibility of the hamstrings and lower back. To perform this activity, the respondent was asked to sit and reach by extending both arms forward reaching as far as possible. In scoring, the farther the distance of the reach, the higher was the level of performance.

Table 18
Male Respondents' Performance Level in Sit and Reach in Pre-test and Post-test

Level of Performance	Frequency	Pre-test Percent	Valid Percent	Frequency	Post-test Percent	Valid Percent
POOR	0	0	0	1	.3	.3
AVERAGE	2	.5	.5	5	1.3	1.3

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GOOD	3	.8	.8	3	.8	.8
VERY GOOD	4	1.0	1.0	3	.8	.8
EXCELLENT	1	.3	.3	3	.8	.8
SUPERIOR	376	97.4	97.4	369	95.6	96.1
Total	386	100.0	100.0	384	99.5	100.0

Table 18 shows the results of the male respondents' level of performance in sit and reach in the pre-test and post-test. The majority of the male respondents were rated superior in this physical activity in both tests. This implies that almost all of them can reach above 23 centimeters while sitting. However, the number of respondents decreased in the post-test. Only one respondent was rated excellent, which signifies that this student could reach 22-23 centimeters in the pre-test, but two more were added in post-test. It can be noted too that four students had the performance level of very good in the pre-test for having reached 20-21 centimeters. However, in the post-test, only three of them were rated very good. Although no one was rated poor during the pre-test, one student performed poorly in the post-test for having reached only below 12 centimeters. Overall, the level of performance among the male respondents was superior which implies that they can perform very well sit and reach. As stated by Kolimechkov (2017), sit and reach is a good physical activity to develop muscular, strength, flexibility, as well as endurance.

Table 19
Female Respondents' Performance Level in Sit and Reach in Pre-test and Post-test

Level of Performance	Pre-test			Post-test		
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
VERY POOR	1	.1	.1	7	.9	.9
POOR	1	.1	.1	10	1.3	1.3
GOOD	11	1.4	1.4	12	1.6	1.6
VERY GOOD	7	.9	.9	11	1.4	1.5
EXCELLENT	6	.8	.8	4	.5	.5
SUPERIOR	735	96.5	96.6	709	93.0	94.2
Total	761	99.9	100.0	753	98.8	100.0

As shown in Table 19, most of the female respondents were rated superior in sit and reach for having reached above 23 centimeters while sitting in both tests; however, a decrease of 26 students can be observed in the post-test. Second in rank were those whose level of performance was good. These were the students who were able to reach 17-19 centimeters during the activity. It can be noted that the number of students in the level increased in one during the post test. What is glaring from the data is the increase in number of those students who were rated very poor and poor from pre-test to post-test. For instance, six students were added to those who were able to reach below 12 centimeters and nine more students were added to those who were able to reach 12-13 centimeters. These results apparently show discrepancies. Overall, the female respondents were able to perform sit and reach with superior level.

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Another physical fitness activity performed by the respondents was the standing Long Jump. This activity assesses lower body strength of the respondents. The level of performance of the respondents was assessed by measuring the distance of the jump from the take-off line to the point where the back of heel lands on the ground.

Table 20
Male Respondents' Performance Level in Standing Long Jump in Pre-test and Post-test

Level of Performance	Pre-test			Post-test		
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
VERY POOR	0	0	0	361	93.5	93.5
POOR	58	15.0	15.0	15	3.9	3.9
AVERAGE	74	19.2	19.2	3	.8	.8
GOOD	109	28.2	28.2	1	.3	.3
VERY GOOD	139	36.0	36.0	6	1.6	1.6
EXCELLENT	6	1.6	1.6	0	0	0
Total	386	100.0	100.0	386	100.0	100.0

Table 20 reveals the results of the male respondents' level of performance in standing long jump during the pre-test and post-test. As seen in the table, no one was rated very poor in the pre-test; however, during the post-test, most of the male respondents had very poor level of performance. This implies that a majority of them were able to reach the distance of 91 centimeters and below. Additionally, almost 40% of the male respondents were rated very good in the pre-test because they were able to reach the distance of 201-250 centimeters in the long jump. However, it is apparent in the data that only six students were able to achieve this level in the post-test. Similarly, almost 30 % of the male respondents were able to achieve the distance of 176-200 centimeters, rating them good during the pre-test. But it can be noted that only one student was able to achieve this level in the post-test. The results show that , in general, the students need improvement in this physical fitness activity.

Table 21
Female Respondents' Performance Level in Standing Long Jump in Pre-test and Post-test

Level of Performance	Pre-test			Post-test		
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
VERY POOR	1	.1	.1	638	83.7	83.7
POOR	111	14.6	14.6	110	14.4	14.4
AVERAGE	253	33.2	33.2	2	.3	.3
GOOD	215	28.2	28.2	2	.3	.3
VERY GOOD	146	19.2	19.2	4	.5	.5

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EXCELLENT	24	3.1	3.1	6	.8	.8
SUPERIOR	12	1.6	1.6	0	0	0
Total	762	100.0	100.0	762	100.0	100.0

It can be noted in Table 21 that almost two percent of the female respondents achieved the superior level in that 12 of them were able to reach the distance of more than 220 centimeters in the standing long jump during the pre-test, but not achieved in the post-test. This was not observed among the male respondents as indicated in Table 20. Another interesting result but alarming is the very poor performance level of most female students in the post-test in that almost 85% only reached the distance of below 51 centimeters in this physical fitness activity. While in the pre-test, only one student performed very poorly. In other words, there was a tremendous change in the female respondents' level of performance as regards standing long jump. It can also be noted that almost 30% of the total female population had good level of performance in the pre-test, but only two students achieved this level in the post test. Based on the data there is a need to improve the performance level of the female students along this area in the same manner as the male respondents do.

Sixty-second sit-up was another physical fitness activity performed by the respondents. Curl-up is an exercise that is good for the endurance of the abdominals. The respondents' level of performance in this activity was measured by the number of sit-ups that the respondents were able to do within 60 seconds.

Table 22
Male Respondents' Performance Level in 60-second Sit-up in Pre-test and Post-test

Level of Performance	Pre-test			Post-test		
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
VERY POOR	160	41.5	41.5	92	23.8	23.8
POOR	193	50.0	50.0	224	58.0	58.0
AVERAGE	20	5.2	5.2	28	7.3	7.3
GOOD	1	.3	.3	9	2.3	2.3
VERY GOOD	5	1.3	1.3	10	2.6	2.6
EXCELLENT	2	.5	.5	10	2.6	2.6
SUPERIOR	5	1.3	1.3	13	3.4	3.4

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Total	386	100.0	100.0	386	100.0	100.0
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It can be deduced from Table 22 that most students had the performance level of poor both in the pre-test and post-test. This implies that most of them were able to reach only 16 sit-ups and below during their performance. It is also noticeable in the table that the number of students who were rated poor increased by 31 students during the post-test. Based on this finding, it can be inferred that students found it difficult to perform this activity. This situation was aggravated by the fact that almost 42% of the male respondents were rated very poor; however, a noticeable decrease can be noted during the post-test. One interesting finding is the increase of eight in the number of students whose performance level was superior during the post-test. This signifies that these students were able to do more than 55 sit-ups. Moreover, an increase in the post-test can be observed in those whose performance levels were good, average, very good and excellent. Overall, it can be deduced that the male respondents considered doing the sit-ups difficult. Hence, the need to improve their physical fitness in this activity.

Table 23
Female Respondents' Performance Level in 60-second Sit-up in Pre-test and Post-test

Level of Performance	Pre-test			Post-test		
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
VERY POOR	0	0	0	205	26.9	26.9
POOR	339	44.5	44.5	377	49.5	49.5
AVERAGE	47	6.2	6.2	85	11.2	11.2
GOOD	8	1.0	1.0	27	3.5	3.5
VERY GOOD	8	1.0	1.0	33	4.3	4.3
EXCELLENT	3	.4	.4	11	1.4	1.4
SUPERIOR	11	1.4	1.4	24	3.1	3.1
Total	762	100.0	100.0	762	100.0	100.0

As can be gleaned in Table 23, when comparing the pre-test and post-test that were used to assess the female respondents in the 60-second sit-up, it is apparent that no one was rated very poor during the pre-test; however, it can be noted that almost 30% of the females had very poor level of performance in the post-test. The result implies that in the post-test 205 females did only 13 sit-ups or less, signifying the difficulty of the activity for them. Notably, there was a noticeable increase in the number of female respondents who had poor level of performance. This means that 38 more females were not able to do the activity with the number of sit-ups that they reached. It is interesting though, to note that those with good, very good, excellent, and superior levels of performance increased in the post-test. There were at least 95 female respondents who were able to do more than 36 sit-ups in 60 seconds. Comparing the male and female respondents, the number of respondents who could do more than 55 sit-ups in the post-test was greater than the male respondents. In general, it can be surmised that it is difficult also for the female respondents to perform the 60-second sit-up as demonstrated by the male respondents. In this regard, it is deemed necessary to improve the level of performance of the female respondents in this physical fitness activity. The study of Mobilia-Jones (2010) does not coincide with the result in the present study because most of the respondents in her study passed the physical activity. The study of Chen (2018) revealed that boys and girls had the same level of performance, and this is also seen in the present study.

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The next activity performed by the respondents was push-ups. This exercise builds up upper body and core strength. The respondents' level of performance in this physical activity was measured by the number of push-ups that they were able to do.

Table 24
Male Respondents' Performance Level in Push-up in Pre-test and Post-test

Level of Performance	Pre-test			Post-test		
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
VERY POOR	218	56.5	56.5	125	32.4	32.4
POOR	70	18.1	18.1	84	21.8	21.8
AVERAGE	69	17.9	17.9	94	24.4	24.4
GOOD	21	5.4	5.4	47	12.2	12.2
VERY GOOD	1	.3	.3	16	4.1	4.1
EXCELLENT	0	0	0	1	.3	.3
SUPERIOR	7	1.8	1.8	19	4.9	4.9
Total	386	100.0	100.0	386	100.0	100.0

Table 24 reveals the results of the male respondents' level of performance in push-up during the pre-test and post-test. As indicated in the table, most of them were classified as very poor in that almost 60% were at this level. This implies that the greatest number of male respondents could do only 19 push-ups or less. In the post-test, the number of students with this level of performance decreased by 93. A little more than 18% of them were rated poor during the pre-test because they only reached 20-24 push-ups. However, the number increased in the post-test. It can be noted, too, that almost 18% were able to achieve the average level in that they were able to do 25-34 push-ups in the pre-test and this increased in the post-test by 6.5%. This means to say that 25 more male respondents were able to reach the expected number of push-ups at this level. It can also be noted that no respondent was rated excellent in the pre-test, but only one was recorded in the post-test. One good result that can be noted is that there was an increase of 12 in the number of students who reached the superior level of performance in the post. This implies that 19 students were able to do 54 sit-ups and above during the post-test. Nevertheless, overall, the male respondents need improvement in this physical fitness activity. This result does not support the study of Mobilla-Jones (2010) in that only a few of the respondents did not pass the test. In the study of Chen, et. al (2018), the male respondents outperformed the female respondents. But in this study, as indicated in the Table 25, more female respondents reached the superior level of performance.

Table 25
Female Respondents' Performance Level in Push-up in Pre-test and Post-test

	Pre-test	Post-test
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Level of Performance	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
VERY POOR	505	66.3	66.3	227	29.8	29.8
POOR	19	2.5	2.5	17	2.2	2.2
AVERAGE	68	8.9	8.9	113	14.8	14.8
GOOD	30	3.9	3.9	66	8.7	8.7
VERY GOOD	52	6.8	6.8	114	15.0	15.0
EXCELLENT	12	1.6	1.6	34	4.5	4.5
SUPERIOR	76	10.0	10.0	191	25.1	25.1
Total	762	100.0	100.0	762	100.0	100.0

As revealed in Table 25, the results are quite similar to the male respondents in that the greatest number of female respondents was rated very poor both in the pre-test and the post test. However, a decrease in the number can be observed in the post-test. One interesting result among the female respondents is that those who achieved the level of superior during the pre-test increased in number in the post-test. This implies that more female respondents were able to do more than 48 push-ups. Comparing the two groups of respondents, it can be deduced that more female respondents had stronger upper body and core. In addition, there were those who were able to reach 46-48 push-ups in the pre-test and the post-test; thereby, they achieved excellence as the level of their performance. Similarly, the number of female respondents increased in the post-test. What is interesting is the number of female respondents who were categorized very poor and poor during the pre-test decreased and those who were able to achieve average increased. Overall, it is still deemed relevant to improve the performance level of the female respondents in this physical fitness exercise.

The respondents were also given the opportunity to perform basic planking as one of their physical fitness activities. Basic planking is an exercise that is good for strength and stability of the body. It helps stabilize balance and power of the body. The level of performance of the respondents was measured on the basis of the number of seconds that they could last doing the basic planking.

Table 26
Respondents' Performance Level in Basic Planking in the Pre-test and Post-test

Level of Performance	Pre-test			Post-test		
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
NEEDS IMPROVEMENT	81	7.1	7.1	144	12.5	12.5
FAIR	223	19.4	19.4	182	15.9	15.9
GOOD	120	10.5	10.5	64	5.6	5.6
VERY GOOD	118	10.3	10.3	146	12.7	12.7
EXCELLENT	606	52.8	52.8	612	53.3	53.3
Total	1148	100.0	100.0	1148	100.0	100.0

Table 26 displays the results of the respondents' performance level in basic planking during the pre-test and post-test. As indicated in the table, more than half of the respondents achieved an excellent level in

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this exercise. This means that they were able to last 51 seconds and above doing the basic planking. In addition, there was an increase in the number of students whose performance level was very good in terms of the pre-test and the post-test. This level of performance indicates that the respondents were able to perform the basic planking in 46-50 seconds. Although there were those whose levels of performance were good and fair in the pre-test, the number decreased in the post-test. This implies that there was an improvement among the respondents as they performed basic planking. Generally, the respondents' performance in the physical fitness activity was remarkable.

To measure the respondents' flexibility and mobility of their upper arms and shoulder joints, the respondents did the zipper test. It is done by reaching one hand behind the neck and down along the spine. After that, the other hand moves behind the back and up toward the top hand. The performance level of the respondents in this activity is measured through how close the hands are in that position to each other. During the performance, the overlaps of the respondents' fingers by centimeter while they were doing the zipper test.

Table 27
Respondents' Performance Level in Zipper Test in terms of the Left Hand in the Pre-test and Post-test

Level of Performance	Pre-test			Post-test		
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
POOR	108	9.4	9.4	149	13.0	13.0
NEEDS IMPROVEMENT	103	9.0	9.0	157	13.7	13.7
FAIR	185	16.1	16.1	201	17.5	17.5
GOOD	152	13.2	13.2	146	12.7	12.7
VERY GOOD	135	11.8	11.8	133	11.6	11.6
EXCELLENT	465	40.5	40.5	362	31.5	31.5
Total	1148	100.0	100.0	1148	100.0	100.0

As can be gleaned in Table 27, almost half of the respondents were able to achieve an excellent level of performance in the zipper test using their left hands during the pre-test. However, there was a decrease in number in the post-test, but still this level had the highest number of respondents as compared to the other levels of performance. This finding indicates that the respondents were able to establish finger overlaps of 6 centimeters or more. Almost 12% of the respondents were able to reach finger overlaps of 4-5.9 centimeters making them achieve a very good level of performance in both tests. It can be noted that there was a bit decrease in the number of students who had good performance level in the post-test as compared to the pre-

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test. The results also show an increase in the number of students who were rated poor, needs improvement and fair. This implies that there were more students who were not able to maintain their performance in the pre-test. Overall, since a good number of students whose level of performance ranged from good to excellent in the post-test, it can be surmised that their performance in this physical fitness test is considered remarkable.

Table 28
Respondents' Performance Level in Zipper Test in terms of the Right Hand in the Pre-test and Post-test

Level of Performance	Pre-test			Post-test		
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
POOR	177	15.4	15.4	351	30.6	30.6
NEEDS IMPROVEMENT	173	15.1	15.1	145	12.6	12.6
FAIR	172	15.0	15.0	129	11.2	11.2
GOOD	136	11.8	11.8	102	8.9	8.9
VERY GOOD	68	5.9	5.9	55	4.8	4.8
EXCELLENT	422	36.8	36.8	366	31.9	31.9
Total	1148	100.0	100.0	1148	100.0	100.0

From the data in Table 28, it can be noted that almost 40% of the respondents were able to let their fingers overlap by 6 centimeters and above making them achieve a performance level of excellent in the pre-test. However, a decrease can be observed in the post-test where almost 32 percent achieved the same level. It can be noted, too, that almost 31 % of the total population were rated very poor in the post-test, almost the same percentage as those whose rating was excellent. In this level, the number of students increased in the post-test as compared to the pre-test. The decrease in number can also be noted in the other performance level. Comparing the respondents' performance in the zipper test using their left and right hands, it can be inferred that their performance was better when using their left hand in this test because the number of students who were able to achieve the levels of good, very good and excellent using the right hand was less than when they used their left hand. In general, respondents' performance passed the average.

The next exercise that the respondents performed was stork balance. This test required the respondents to stand on one leg, up on the ball of the foot, for as long as possible. The stork balance assesses the balance ability of the whole body as well as endurance because the level of performance of the respondents was measured on the basis of how long they could do the activity.

Table 29
Respondents' Performance Level in Stork Balance Test (Right Leg) in the Pre-test and Post-test

Level of Performance	Pre-test			Post-test		
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent

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NEEDS IMPROVEMENT	1021	88.9	88.9	863	75.2	75.2
FAIR	91	7.9	7.9	226	19.7	19.7
GOOD	16	1.4	1.4	25	2.2	2.2
VERY GOOD	13	1.1	1.1	13	1.1	1.1
EXCELLENT	7	.6	.6	21	1.8	1.8
Total	1148	100.0	100.0	1148	100.0	100.0

Table 29 shows the respondents' level of performance in the right leg stork balance test during the pre-test and post-test. As revealed in the table, almost 90% of the respondents had the performance level of needs improvement in the pre-test and a little bit higher than 75% in the post-test. This finding implies that the respondents were able to perform the task in only 1-40 seconds. Hence, their endurance and body balance were not that strong. Those whose performance level was fair in the pre-test increased in number in the post-test. It can be observed that almost 2% of the respondents achieved an excellent level and it increased in the post-test. Based on the data, it can be concluded that in this physical fitness activity, the respondents need to improve.

Table 30
Respondents' Performance Level in Stork Balance Test (Left Leg) in the Pre-test and Post-test

Level of Performance	Pre-test			Post-test		
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
NEEDS IMPROVEMENT	1055	91.9	91.9	1132	98.6	98.6
FAIR	60	5.2	5.2	13	1.1	1.1
GOOD	10	.9	.9	1	.1	.1
VERY GOOD	18	1.6	1.6	1	.1	.1
EXCELLENT	5	.4	.4	1	.1	.1
Total	1148	100.0	100.0	1148	100.0	100.0

Indicated in Table 30 are the results in the pre-test and post-test of the respondents' level of performance in left-leg stork balance. A majority of the respondents needed improvement in this physical fitness activity. It means that they were able to perform the activity in only 1-40 seconds. Five respondents were able to achieve an excellent level in the pre-test; however, in the post-test, only one was able to accomplish the task excellently. What is glaring in the result was the decrease in the number of students who earned the level of very good. In the pretest, there were 18 students who were able to last for 121- 160 seconds doing the left-leg stork balance, but in the post-test, only one was able to achieve this level. Similarly, 10 students were rated good in the pre-test, but only one in the post-test. A drastic decrease in the number of students who perform the tasks fairly in the pre-test can be observed, from 60 students to 13 students in the post-test. Hence, the same conclusion can be drawn that students need to improve their level of performance in the left-leg stork balance.

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The last physical fitness activity performed by the respondents was shuttle run. This activity usually involves continuous running back and forth between two-line markers at a certain pace, and vary in degrees of intensity, duration, and distance. This physical fitness test assesses speed, agility, and cardiorespiratory fitness. The respondents' level of performance was measured by the number of seconds they were able to do the task since this assesses speed and agility. This means that every respondent should have run three times bringing the blocks to the other side completely.

Table 31
Respondents' Performance Level in Shuttle Run in the Pre-test and Post-test

Level of Performance	Pre-test			Post-test		
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent
NEEDS IMPROVEMENT	13	1.1	1.1	22	1.9	1.9
FAIR	171	14.9	14.9	85	7.4	7.4
GOOD	542	47.2	47.2	461	40.2	40.2
VERY GOOD	383	33.4	33.4	506	44.1	44.1
EXCELLENT	39	3.4	3.4	74	6.4	6.4
Total	1148	100.0	100.0	1148	100.0	100.0

Based on Table 31, about 4% of the respondents achieved an excellent level in the pre-test while almost 7% in the post-test. The highest number of respondents were rated good in the pre-test. This implies that several respondents were able to perform the activity properly in that they were able to do the task for 21-25 seconds. However, it can be observed that the percentage dropped to 40.2 in the post-test. Additionally, there were almost 35% among the respondents with the rating of very good. The percentage increased to 44.1% in the post-test implying that these respondents were able to perform the task within 16-20 seconds. Generally, the performance level of the respondents showed a remarkable performance based on the number of students who achieved good, very good, and excellent levels of performance in shuttle run. Kolimechkov (2017) suggests that shuttle run is a very good exercise for the improvement of cardiorespiratory fitness.

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To provide the general picture of the respondents' performance in all the physical fitness activities the following summary tables are provided.

Table 32
Summary Table of the Respondents' Performance in the Physical Fitness Activities

	Zipper Test (Left): Flexibility	
Pre-test		Post-test
Excellent		Excellent
	Zipper Test (right)	
Excellent		Excellent
	Stork balance (Right): Leg Strength and Balance	
Pre-test		Post-test
Needs Improvement		Needs Improvement
	Stork balance (Left):	
Pre-test		Post-test
Needs Improvement		Needs improvement
	Planking: General Endurance	
Pre-test		Post-test
Excellent		Excellent
	Shuttle Run: Agility	
Pre-test		Post-test
Good		Very Good
	40 M Sprint (Female): Speed	
Pre-test		Post-test
Needs Improvement		Need Improvement
	40 M Sprint (Male): Speed	
Pre-test		Post-test
Fair		Good
	Push-up (Female): Strength and Endurance	
Pre-test		Post-test
Very Poor		Very Poor
	Push-up (Male):	
Very Poor		Very Poor
	Sit and Reach (Female): Flexibility	
Pre-test		Post-test
Superior		Superior
	Sit and Reach (Male): Flexibility	
Pre-test		Post-test
Superior		Superior
	Standing Long Jump (Female): Leg strength and power	
Pre-test		Post-test
Average		Good

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Standing Long Jump (Male)

Pre-test	Post-test
Very Poor	Very Good
60-second Sit-Up (Female): Abdominal strength and endurance	
Pre-test	Post-test
Poor	Poor

60-second Sit-Up (Male)

Pre-test	Post-test
Poor	Poor

Based on Table 32, the respondents were rated excellent in the post-test in the following physical activities: left and right zipper test and planking. In addition, the students were rated superior in sit and reach during the post-test. Further, they achieved a very good performance level in shuttle run and standing log jump among the male. In this activity, the female respondents were rated good in the post-. Based on these results, the respondents' performance level was considered remarkable, and they need to sustain such performance or do more to improve their performance. Among the different physical activities, the respondents needed to improve in the following activities: left and right stork balance and 40 M sprint for female, but good for male. They were rated very poor in the post-test in push-up, and poor in 60-second sit-up. These results imply that the respondents need to do something to improve their performance in these exercises to develop their strength, endurance, and speed. Thus, the self-help physical activities in a module format are deemed relevant to the students. These results do not corroborate the study of Giron (2008) in that the college students surpassed the standards set by CHED in the different physical activities tested.

Table 33
Summary of the Physical Fitness Concepts Developed by the Physical Fitness Tests

Physical Fitness Test	Physical Fitness Concepts It Developed	Result	
		Pretest	Post Test
60-SECOND SIT-UP	Abdominal Strength and Endurance	Poor -Male & Female	Poor – Male & Female
40 M SPRINT	Speed	Fair – Male Needs Improvement - Female	Good – Male Needs Improvement - Female
PLANKING	General Endurance	Excellent	Excellent
PUSH UP	Arm Strength and Endurance	Very Poor – Male & Female	Very Poor - Male & Female
SHUTTLE RUN	Agility	Good	Very Good
SIT AND REACH	Flexibility	Superior -Male & Female	Superior - Male & Female
STANDING LONG JUMP	Leg Strength and Power	Very poor -Male Average - Female	Very good -Male Good - Female
STORK BALANCE (Right & Left)	Leg Strength and Balance	Needs Improvement	Needs Improvement
ZIPPER TEST (Right and Left)	Flexibility	Excellent	Excellent

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As indicated in Table 33 and also mentioned in the previous discussions, the respondents need to improve their abdominal strength and endurance by doing the 60-second sit-up; speed by performing the 40 M sprint; arm strength and endurance by doing push up; and leg strength and balance by doing the stork and balance exercise. In the same manner, they need to sustain their general endurance, agility, leg strength and power, and flexibility by continually performing physical fitness exercises such as planking, shuttle, sit and reach, standing long jump, and zipper test.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Conclusions:

Based on the results, the following conclusions are derived:

1. The age of the respondents varies with most respondents aging 18; more female respondents participated in the study; most respondents are underweight and considered ectomorph.
2. The respondents are generally ready to undergo physical activities.
3. In terms of the respondents' level of performance in the physical fitness tests, they need to improve on the aspects of abdominal strength and endurance, speed, arm strength and endurance, and leg strength and balance. However, they are excellent in terms of general endurance, superior in flexibility and very good in agility.

Recommendations:

Based on the findings, the researchers strongly recommend the following:

1. Include more activities that will develop their leg strength and balance, speed specifically for female, arm strength and endurance, and abdominal strength and endurance, stork balance, 40 – meter sprint, push-ups, and curl-ups respectively.
2. Arm strengthening exercise should be done regularly, since no arm exercises were done during the pandemic, only the fingers were exercised, the arms were weak, thus getting a very poor performance rating in push-ups.
3. Allocate more time for the administration of the physical fitness test and intervention activities, with close monitoring of the conduct PFT as a whole.
4. Physical education classes are only scheduled for two hours per week. With this time frame, the students will not be able accomplish their physical fitness test activities and the given interventions to them. Therefore, to ensure students' growth and development, the conduct of intervention activities should be carried out on an everyday basis for these to become part of their lifestyle.

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5. Physical fitness tests and intervention activities should take place not only in students' PATH FIT classes, but these should be regarded as self-help physical activities. Hence, a module that contains the self-help physical activities is deemed necessary.
6. For future research, it is recommended that variables such as academic performance, lifestyle, and neural-mental activities be correlated with the performance level of physical fitness tests among students.

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http://www.emunix.edu/~bogle/fitness_testing_table.htm

<http://www.peworld.org/fitness/testing.htm>

<http://www.topendsports.com/testing/tests.htm>

Appendices

Copy of the Student's Physical Fitness Card and PARR-Q

PARQ+ FORM

The Physical Activity Readiness Questionnaire (PARQ+) is considered as a primary screening tool for Physical Activity, Fitness and Physical Exercise (Warburton et al., 2010). The PARQ+ is also an internationally renowned pre-participation screening tool being done conducting physical activities to determine and identify any possible restrictions or limitations to Physical activity participation. PARQ+ has undergone extensive evaluation with healthy asymptomatic symptomatic populations. It important to highlight the role that the play in reducing barriers to physical activity participation.

2022 PAR-Q+
FOLLOW-UP QUESTIONS ABOUT YOUR MEDICAL CONDITION(S)

1. Do you have Arthritis, Osteoporosis, or Back Problems?
If the above condition(s) is/are present, answer questions 1a-1c. If NO go to question 2

1a. Do you have difficulty controlling your condition with medications or other physician-prescribed therapies? (Answer NO if you are not currently taking medications or other treatments) YES NO

1b. Do you have joint problems causing pain, a recent fracture or fracture caused by osteoporosis or cancer, displaced vertebra (e.g., spondylolisthesis), and/or spondylolysis/pars defect (a crack in the bony ring on the back of the spinal column)? YES NO

1c. Have you had steroid injections or taken steroid tablets regularly for more than 3 months? YES NO

2. Do you currently have Cancer of any kind?
If the above condition(s) is/are present, answer questions 2a-2b. If NO go to question 3

2a. Does your cancer diagnosis include any of the following types: lung/breast/cervical, multiple myeloma (cancer of plasma cells), head, and/or neck? YES NO

2b. Are you currently receiving cancer therapy (such as chemotherapy or radiotherapy)? YES NO

3. Do you have a Heart or Cardiovascular Condition? This includes Coronary Artery Disease, Heart Failure, Diagnosed Abnormality of Heart Rhythm
If the above condition(s) is/are present, answer questions 3a-3d. If NO go to question 4

3a. Do you have difficulty controlling your condition with medications or other physician-prescribed therapies? (Answer NO if you are not currently taking medications or other treatments) YES NO

3b. Do you have an irregular heart beat that requires medical management? (e.g., atrial fibrillation, premature ventricular contractions) YES NO

3c. Do you have chronic heart failure? YES NO

3d. Do you have diagnosed coronary artery (atherosclerotic) disease and have not participated in regular physical activity in the last 2 months? YES NO

4. Do you currently have High Blood Pressure?
If the above condition(s) is/are present, answer questions 4a-4b. If NO go to question 5

4a. Do you have difficulty controlling your condition with medications or other physician-prescribed therapies? (Answer NO if you are not currently taking medications or other treatments) YES NO

4b. Do you have a resting blood pressure equal to or greater than 160/90 mmHg with or without medication? (Answer YES if you do not know your resting blood pressure) YES NO

5. Do you have any Metabolic Conditions? This includes Type 1 Diabetes, Type 2 Diabetes, Pre-Diabetes
If the above condition(s) is/are present, answer questions 5a-5e. If NO go to question 6

5a. Do you often have difficulty controlling your blood sugar levels with foods, medications, or other physician-prescribed therapies? YES NO

5b. Do you often suffer from signs and symptoms of low blood sugar (hypoglycemia) following exercise and/or during activities of daily living? Signs of hypoglycemia may include shakiness, nervousness, unusual irritability, abnormal sweating, dizziness or light-headedness, mental confusion, difficulty speaking, weakness, or sleepiness. YES NO

5c. Do you have any signs or symptoms of diabetes complications such as heart or vascular disease and/or complications affecting your eyes, kidneys, OR the sensation in your toes and feet? YES NO

5d. Do you have other metabolic conditions (such as current pregnancy-related diabetes, chronic kidney disease, or liver problems)? YES NO

5e. Are you planning to engage in what for you is unusually high (or vigorous) intensity exercise in the near future? YES NO

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- 6. Do you have any Mental Health Problems or Learning Difficulties?** This includes Alzheimer's, Dementia, Depression, Anxiety Disorder, Eating Disorder, Psychotic Disorder, Intellectual Disability, Down Syndrome. If the above condition(s) is/are present, answer questions 6a-6b. If **NO** go to question 7.
- 6a. Do you have difficulty controlling your condition with medications or other physician-prescribed therapies? (Answer **NO** if you are not currently taking medications or other treatments) YES NO
- 6b. Do you have Down Syndrome **AND** back problems affecting nerves or muscles? YES NO
-
- 7. Do you have a Respiratory Disease?** This includes Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease, Asthma, Pulmonary High Blood Pressure. If the above condition(s) is/are present, answer questions 7a-7d. If **NO** go to question 8.
- 7a. Do you have difficulty controlling your condition with medications or other physician-prescribed therapies? (Answer **NO** if you are not currently taking medications or other treatments) YES NO
- 7b. Has your doctor ever said your blood oxygen level is low at rest or during exercise and/or that you require supplemental oxygen therapy? YES NO
- 7c. If asthmatic, do you currently have symptoms of chest tightness, wheezing, laboured breathing, consistent cough (more than 2 days/week), or have you used your rescue medication more than twice in the last week? YES NO
- 7d. Has your doctor ever said you have high blood pressure in the blood vessels of your lungs? YES NO
-
- 8. Do you have a Spinal Cord Injury?** This includes Tetraplegia and Paraplegia. If the above condition(s) is/are present, answer questions 8a-8c. If **NO** go to question 9.
- 8a. Do you have difficulty controlling your condition with medications or other physician-prescribed therapies? (Answer **NO** if you are not currently taking medications or other treatments) YES NO
-
- 9. Have you had a Stroke?** This includes Transient Ischemic Attack (TIA) or Cerebrovascular Event. If the above condition(s) is/are present, answer questions 9a-9c. If **NO** go to question 10.
- 9a. Do you have difficulty controlling your condition with medications or other physician-prescribed therapies? (Answer **NO** if you are not currently taking medications or other treatments) YES NO
- 9b. Do you have any impairment in walking or mobility? YES NO
- 9c. Have you experienced a stroke or impairment in nerves or muscles in the past 6 months? YES NO
-
- 10. Do you have any other medical condition not listed above or do you have two or more medical conditions?** If you have other medical conditions, answer questions 10a-10c. If **NO** read the Page 4 recommendations.
- 10a. Have you experienced a blackout, fainted, or lost consciousness as a result of a head injury within the last 12 months **OR** have you had a diagnosed concussion within the last 12 months? YES NO
- 10b. Do you have a medical condition that is not listed (such as epilepsy, neurological conditions, kidney problems)? YES NO
- 10c. Do you currently live with two or more medical conditions? YES NO

PLEASE LIST YOUR MEDICAL CONDITION(S) AND ANY RELATED MEDICATIONS HERE:

GO to Page 4 for recommendations about your current medical condition(s) and sign the PARTICIPANT DECLARATION.

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The Physical Activity Readiness Questionnaire for Everyone

The health benefits of regular physical activity are clear; more people should engage in physical activity every day of the week. Participating in physical activity is very safe for MOST people. This questionnaire will tell you whether it is necessary for you to seek further advice from your doctor. **OR** a qualified exercise professional before becoming more physically active.

GENERAL HEALTH QUESTIONS

Please read the 7 questions below carefully and answer each one honestly; check YES or NO.

	YES	NO
1) Has your doctor ever said that you have a heart condition <input type="checkbox"/> OR high blood pressure <input type="checkbox"/> ?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2) Do you feel pain in your chest at rest, during your daily activities of living, OR when you do physical activity?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3) Do you lose balance because of dizziness OR have you lost consciousness in the last 12 months? <small>Please answer NO if your dizziness was associated with over-breathing (including during vigorous exercise).</small>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4) Have you ever been diagnosed with another chronic medical condition (other than heart disease or high blood pressure)? PLEASE LIST CONDITION(S) HERE: _____	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5) Are you currently taking prescribed medications for a chronic medical condition? PLEASE LIST CONDITION(S) AND MEDICATIONS HERE: _____	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6) Do you currently have (or have had within the past 12 months) a bone, joint, or soft tissue (muscle, ligament, or tendon) problem that could be made worse by becoming more physically active? <small>Please answer NO if you had a problem in the past, but it does not limit your current ability to be physically active.</small> PLEASE LIST CONDITION(S) HERE: _____	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
7) Has your doctor ever said that you should only do medically supervised physical activity?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

If you answered NO to all of the questions above, you are cleared for physical activity. Please sign the PARTICIPANT DECLARATION. You do not need to complete Pages 2 and 3.

- Start becoming much more physically active – start slowly and build up gradually.
- Follow Global Physical Activity Guidelines for your age (<https://www.who.int/publications/i/item/9789240015128>).
- You may take part in a health and fitness appraisal.
- If you are over the age of 45 yr and NOT accustomed to regular vigorous to maximal effort exercise, consult a qualified exercise professional before engaging in this intensity of exercise.
- If you have any further questions, contact a qualified exercise professional.

PARTICIPANT DECLARATION
 If you are less than the legal age required for consent or require the assent of a care provider, your parent, guardian or care provider must also sign this form.

I, the undersigned, have read, understood to my full satisfaction and completed this questionnaire. I acknowledge that this physical activity clearance is valid for a maximum of 12 months from the date it is completed and becomes invalid if my condition changes. I also acknowledge that the community/fitness center may retain a copy of this form for its records. In these instances, it will maintain the confidentiality of the same, complying with applicable law.

NAME _____ DATE _____
 SIGNATURE _____ WITNESS _____
 SIGNATURE OF PARENT/GUARDIAN/CARE PROVIDER _____

If you answered YES to one or more of the questions above, COMPLETE PAGES 2 AND 3.

Delay becoming more active if:

- You have a temporary illness such as a cold or fever; it is best to wait until you feel better.
- You are pregnant - talk to your health care practitioner, your physician, a qualified exercise professional, and/or complete the ePARmed-X4 at www.spartamedx.com before becoming more physically active.
- Your health changes - answer the questions on Pages 2 and 3 of this document and/or talk to your doctor or a qualified exercise professional before continuing with any physical activity program.

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✓ If you answered NO to all of the FOLLOW-UP questions (pgs. 2-3) about your medical condition, you are ready to become more physically active - sign the PARTICIPANT DECLARATION below:

- It is advised that you consult a qualified exercise professional to help you develop a safe and effective physical activity plan to meet your health needs.
- You are encouraged to start slowly and build up gradually - 20 to 60 minutes of low to moderate intensity exercise, 3-5 days per week including aerobic and muscle strengthening exercises.
- As you progress, you should aim to accumulate 150 minutes or more of moderate intensity physical activity per week.
- If you are over the age of 45 yr and **NOT** accustomed to regular vigorous to maximal effort exercise, consult a qualified exercise professional before engaging in this intensity of exercise.

• If you answered YES to one or more of the follow-up questions about your medical condition: You should seek further information before becoming more physically active or engaging in a fitness appraisal. You should complete the specially designed online screening and exercise recommendations program - the **ePARmed-X+** at www.ePARmed-X.com and/or visit a qualified exercise professional to work through the ePARmed-X+ and for further information.

⚠ Delay becoming more active if:

- You have a temporary illness such as a cold or fever; it is best to wait until you feel better.
- You are pregnant - talk to your health care practitioner, your physician, a qualified exercise professional, and/or complete the ePARmed-X+ at www.ePARmed-X.com before becoming more physically active.
- Your health changes - talk to your doctor or qualified exercise professional before continuing with any physical activity program.

• You are encouraged to photocopy the PAR-Q+. You must use the entire questionnaire and NO changes are permitted.

• The authors, the PAR-Q+ Collaboration, partner organizations, and their agents assume no liability for persons who undertake physical activity and/or make use of the PAR-Q+ or ePARmed-X+. If in doubt after completing the questionnaire, consult your doctor prior to physical activity.

PARTICIPANT DECLARATION

• All persons who have completed the PAR-Q+ please read and sign the declaration below.

• If you are less than the legal age required for consent or require the assent of a care provider, your parent, guardian or care provider must also sign this form.

I, the undersigned, have read, understood to my full satisfaction and completed this questionnaire. I acknowledge that this physical activity clearance is valid for a maximum of 12 months from the date it is completed and becomes invalid if my condition changes. I also acknowledge that the community/fitness center may retain a copy of this form for records. In these instances, it will maintain the confidentiality of the same, complying with applicable law.

NAME _____ DATE _____

SIGNATURE _____ WITNESS _____

SIGNATURE OF PARENT/GUARDIAN/CARE PROVIDER _____

For more information, please contact
www.ePARmed-X.com
Email: eparmedx@gmail.com

Notice for PAR-Q+
The PAR-Q+ (PAR-Q+, PARmed-X+, and ePARmed-X+) is a product of the PARmed-X+ Collaboration.
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PHYSICAL FITNESS TEST SCORE CARD

Inspired by Mission,
Driven by Excellence

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PART 2: SKILL RELATED FITNESS

A. Coordination: Juggling Score:

B. Agility: Hexagon Agility Test

Clockwise: Time (00:00)	Counterclockwise: Time (00:00)	Average

C. Speed: 40 m Sprint Time:

D. Power: Standing Long Jump

Distance(Centimeters)	
First Trial	Second Trial

E. Balance: Stork Balance Stand test

Right Foot: Time (00:00)	Left Foot: Time (00:00)

F. Stick Drop Test

1 st Trial	2 nd Trial	3 rd Trial	Middle Score

Number of Push Ups	Time	Number of Push Ups

D. Flexibility

1. Zipper test

2. Sit and Reach

Overlap/Gap (centimeters)	
Left	Right

Score (centimeters)		
First Try	Second Try	Best Score

The form shows the different activities in each Physical Fitness component to be executed by the students. It is divided into two categories (*Health Related and Skill Related components*) where some of the activities made use of a timer/stopwatch and ruler/meter sticks for the other activities. Moreover, pre-test and post-test was administered using the same form/score card.

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The Intervention Activities

Interventions are activities that are set or used to help students become successful in their classwork, to achieve a desired result overcoming weaknesses and to decrease negative from positive results. This is achieved based on students' needs and available resources which target academic or behavior or physical challenges.

In Physical Education, strengths and weaknesses are identified through their performance on either skill related or health related physical fitness activities which are conducted twice a year. The results of which may be sustained, improved through physical, social, emotional, individual interventions that focus on changing physical activity behavior and becoming aware of health conditions.

The intervention activities can be done as a group or personalized to every individual's need. Thus, results of the Pre-test serve as basis to provide a plan of activity and shall be used to improve such.

The health- related physical activities however made use of the following intervention activities.

1. Repetition of the different positions where most exercises begin.
2. Stunts activities such as the individual and dual stunts (dog walk, crab walk, coffee grinder, measuring inch worm, seal crawl, wheel borrow, double bear and table)
3. Specific activities for developing core and muscular strength such as.

Push Ups/Plank

- Planks (prone position where legs are extended and hands on the floor that serve as the base. Body is extended straight parallel to the floor)
- Elevated push-up (facing the wall, do the push – up while on standing position)
- Oblique twisting (in a hook sitting, body is twisted either right or left)
- Flutter kicks (in a lying position, legs are raised /lifted while legs alternately kicking up and down)
- **Weight Training (lift lighter weights with a higher rep range)**

Cardiovascular

- Jogging
- Brisk Walking
- Aerobic Dancing, Zumba

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Flexibility

- Dynamic Stretching (Shoulder Rotation, trunk twists, leg swing, lunges)
- Static Stretching

Muscular Endurance

- Biking, Running, Swimming
- Weight Training 2 -3 x per week

The skill- related components such as Balance (Stork Test) , Coordination, Agility(Shuttle Run), Speed (40 meter) , Power (Standing Long Jump) and Reaction Time (Ruler test)

Balance

- Alternating knee lifts while walking
- Heels raise
- Standing up and sitting down from a chair without using hands
- On a standing position, place your hands on while doing a push up facing the wall but with less weight. Simply place your hands on the elevated surface. Keep your body in an inclined/straight line and perform a push up.

Agility

- Jogging and running with high knee lift (heels click, jumping jack)
- Ladder drills using high knee marks.
- Cone drills (Touch each cone that creates a letter of their choice by moving through a pace that suits the performer. He may use skip, run, jump or shuffle)

Speed

- Jogging, running (with high knee lift), (heels click, jumping jack)
- Lunges (forward, backward, sideward, deep lunges)
- Jumping with rope

As every individual commits to these basic interventions daily or at least four times a week, one is able to teach the body a new channel that overcomes one's weaknesses and thus creates a new lifestyle or new habit. When one consistently does the intervention every session, the activity is more likely to become a lasting habit and improved fitness. Thus, these interventions may be a guide or basis of creating customizable fitness program for all fitness levels that aims for good form.

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SAMPLE FITNESS WEEK PLAN

(Utilizing the intervention activities-with an increased counts and repetitions)

MONDAY	TUESDAY	WEDNESDAY	THURSDAY	FRIDAY	SATURDAY	SUNDAY
Lower-Body Bodyweight Workout <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Jogging and running with high knee lift ➤ Ladder drills ➤ Cone drills ➤ Lunges ➤ Jumping with rope ➤ Leg Raises 	Upper-Body Bodyweight Workout <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Jogging ➤ Brisk Walking ➤ Aerobic Dancing, Zumba ➤ Planks ➤ Elevated push-up ➤ Arm Slides ➤ Side Planks ➤ Boat Pose 	Cross-Training <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Cycling ➤ Swimming ➤ Yoga ➤ Doing household activities 	Total-Body Bodyweight Workout <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Jogging and running with high knee Lift ➤ Aerobic Dancing, Zumba ➤ Plank Twists ➤ Leg Raises 	Abs Workout Of 3 sets or more <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Crunches (15 - 20 reps) ➤ Flutter kick (10-15 reps) ➤ Planks (2-5) ➤ Elevated push-up (15 - 20 reps) ➤ Bridge Exercise (10-15 reps) 	Cross-Training <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Cycling ➤ Swimming ➤ Yoga ➤ Doing household activities 	REST

Note:

- Activities may be done with 3 or more sets depending on the strength of the performer until tired.

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- Each activity such as lunges, raises, planks, push -ups may be done with a minimum of 10 reps or a maximum of 20 reps. Number of repetitions vary accordingly depending on the desired amount of time, duration, frequency, energy and the type exerted by the performer (based on FITT Principle of Exercise)
- Jogging and running activities may be done for 15 minutes or more
- Side planks and Boat Pose may be done for 15 seconds or until tired.
- Focus on diet too, as to when these activities are executed.

Physical Fitness Test Purpose, Equipment, Procedure and Scoring

Zipper Test

Purpose -to test the flexibility of the shoulder girdle.

Equipment: Ruler/Meter Stick

Procedure

For the Tester:

- Stand erect.
 - Raise your right arm, bend your elbow, and reach down across your back as far as possible, to test the right shoulder; extend your left arm down and behind your back, bend your elbow up across your back, and try to reach/cross your fingers over those of your right hand as if to pull a zipper or scratch between the shoulder blades.
- To test the left shoulder, repeat procedures a and b with the left hand over the left shoulder.

For the Partner:

- Observe whether the fingers touched or overlapped each other, if not, measure the gap between the middle fingers of both hands.
- Record the distance in centimeters.

Scoring - record zipper test to the nearest 0.1 centimeter

Score	Standard	Interpretation
5	Fingers overlapped by 6 cm. and above	Excellent
4	Fingers overlapped by 4 - 5.9 cm.	Very Good
3	Fingers overlapped by 2 - 3.9 cm	Good
2	Fingers overlapped by 0.1 - 1.9 cm.	Fair
1	Just touched the fingers	Needs Improvement
0	Gap of 0.1 or wider	Poor

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Stork Balance Test

Purpose - to assess one's ability to maintain equilibrium.

Equipment:

flat, non-slip surface

Stopwatch

Procedure

For the Tester:

1. Remove the shoes and place hands on the hips.
2. Position the right foot on the side of the knee of the left foot.
3. Raise the left heel to balance on the ball of the foot.
4. Do the same procedure with the opposite foot.

For the Partner:

1. Start the time as the heel of the performer is raised off the floor.
2. Stop the time if any of the following occurs:
 - the hand(s) come off the hips
 - the supporting foot swivels or moves (hops) in any direction
 - the non-supporting foot loses contact with the knee. the heel of the supporting foot touches the floor.
3. There shall be three (3) trials.

Scoring - Record the time taken on both feet in nearest seconds and divide the score to two (2) to get the average percentage score.

Score	Age	9 - 12	13 - 14	15 - 16	17 and above	Interpretation
5		41 – 60 sec.	81 – 100 sec.	121 – 150 sec.	161 – 180 sec.	Excellent
4		31 – 40 sec.	61 – 80 sec.	91 – 120 sec.	121 – 160 sec.	Very Good
3		21 – 30 sec.	41 – 60 sec.	61 – 90 sec.	81 – 120 sec.	Good
2		11 – 20 sec.	21 – 40 sec.	31 – 60 sec.	41 – 80 sec.	Fair
1		1 – 10 sec.	1 – 20 sec.	1 – 30 sec.	1 – 40 sec.	Needs Improvement

40-meter sprint

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Purpose - to measure running speed.

Equipment:

1. Stopwatch
2. Running area with known measurement (40 meters)

Procedure:

For the Tester:

- a. At the signal "Ready", stand behind the take-off line, the tips of the shoes should not go beyond the line and assume a crouch position.
- b. At the signal "Get Set, assume an un-crouch position (buttocks up) with both hands on the starting line.
- c. At the signal "GO", run to the finish line as fast as you can.

For the Partner:

- a. Set the stopwatch to zero (0) point.
- b. At the signal "GO" start the watch and stop it as the performer crossed the finish line.
- c. Record time in the nearest 0:00:01 seconds

Scoring - Record the time in nearest minutes and seconds.

Standard Norms in Seconds								
Age	Boys				Girls			
	9 - 12	13 - 14	15 - 16	17 and above	9 - 12	13 - 14	15 - 16	17 and above
Excellent	<6.0	<5.0	<4.5	<4.0	<7.0	<6.5	<5.5	<4.5
Very Good	6.1 - 7.7	5.1 - 6.9	4.6 - 5.4	4.1 - 5.4	7.1 - 8.4	6.6 - 7.6	5.6 - 6.1	4.6 - 5.9
Good	7.8 - 8.5	7.0 - 8.0	5.5 - 7.0	5.5 - 6.5	8.5 - 9.5	7.7 - 8.8	6.2 - 7.2	6.0 - 7.0
Fair	9.5 - 8.6	8.1 - 9.1	7.1 - 8.1	6.6 - 7.5	9.6 - 10.5	8.9 - 9.5	7.3 - 8.5	7.1 - 8.1
Needs Improvement	>9.6	>9.2	>8.2	>7.6	>10.6	>9.6	>8.6	>8.2

Basic Plank

Purpose - to measure strength/stability of the core muscles.

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Equipment: exercise mats or any clean mat, stopwatch/time piece

Procedure:

For the Tester:

- Assume a push - up position. Rest body on forearms with palms and fingers flat on the floor. Elbows are aligned with the shoulders.
- Legs are straight with ankles, knees and thighs touching together.
- Support weight on forearms and toes; make sure that your back is flat. Head, neck and spine are in a straight line.
- Keep abdominals engaged/contracted; do not let stomach drop or allow hips to rise.

For the Partner:

- Ensure the availability of a mat/smooth flooring or anything that can protect the forearms.
- Give the signal "Start/Go" and start/press the time piece.
- Make sure that the back of the head, neck, spine, and ankles are in a straight line.
- Give two (2) warnings.
- Stop the time when the performer can no longer hold the required position, or, when the performer has held the position for at least 90 seconds. Holding the plank position beyond 90 seconds is considered unnecessary.

Scoring - record the time in the nearest seconds/minute. Maximum of 90 seconds for Boys and Girls

Score	Standard	Interpretation
5	51 seconds and above	Excellent
4	46 - 50 seconds	Very Good
3	31 - 45 seconds	Good
2	16 - 30 seconds	Fair
1	1 - 15 seconds	Needs Improvement

Shuttle Run

Purpose-To test the agility of the students.

Equipment: Meter stick/Measuring Tape, Stones

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Procedure:

- Set up markers such as box/circle about 5 meters apart.
- Place 5 stones inside the markers
- Get into sprinter position. Sprint as fast as you can to the other marker.
- Grab one of the stones with your hand and immediately turn around and sprint back to the starting marker.
- Do it until done.

Standard	Interpretation	Score
10-15	Excellent	5
16-20	Very Good	4
21-25	Good	3
26-30	Needs Improvement	2
31-above	Poor	1

